

Sensitive Data: Persistent Identifier (PID) Semantics Gaps

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Introduction & PID/Version Overview

The ethos that digital objects of relevance to researchers should be as open as possible, and as protected as necessary, is at the foundation of ensuring that impactful research remains legal and ethical.

Digital objects may consist of data, structured metadata and associated less structured documentation. The management of discrete digital objects (including research data, but also software, publications and other types) requires that they be clearly identified. To maintain a trustworthy chain of provenance, as objects are changed, split and merged through their lifecycle new identifiers may be assigned and/or their associated change/version metadata updated.

Values held in SQL database rows, for example, are tightly coupled to their primary key identifiers in a locally controlled environment. In contrast, persistent identifier systems provide a solution that supports the local *and remote* application of identifiers to digital objects and parts of digital objects. The remote aspect of their functionality is supported by associating the identifier with resolution information that routes a user to a target.

In practice, a persistent identifier does not always route directly to the digital object itself. A PID service provider provides a resolution process using a defined protocol and the PID manager provides a target location, which could be a landing page or catalogue record that contains metadata about the digital object or even another target location. Information may be provided at each location about how to continue the next step on the journey to the digital object itself. We trust the system of PID service providers and digital object managers to ensure that this ‘transitive dereferencing’ will eventually reach a digital object.

The FAIR Principles envisage that both the ‘data’ and the ‘metadata’ should be persistently identified. In practice, when repositories assign a PID to a digital object, there is often an implied and assumed association with the associated PID Service metadata and intermediate metadata e.g. a single PID resolves to a landing page and or catalogue record, which routes to the digital object.

If *any* change to the digital object requires that a new PID is generated then metadata may be used to associate an object with previous versions of the object (e.g. “is derived from”). If *any* part of the digital object identified by a PID is permitted to change without assigning a new PID then the digital object may be accompanied by change/version metadata (version number, change log, etc).

Parts of a digital object (data, metadata, documentation, individual files, and individual variables) may be assigned their own PIDs and associated metadata. Changes to these ‘parts’ may influence changes (new PIDs, or new versions) to surrounding parts of the object.

There may be barriers to accessing digital objects directly or transitively, even for data that is defined as ‘open’, and is accompanied by an appropriate open licence, typically but not

exclusively Creative Commons. These barriers, which may apply to humans and/or machines, could include a requirement that a user logs in, or 'clicks through' to accept terms and conditions. In these cases, the barriers to access may be driven by an organisation's legal, ethical and policy obligations, but they are not necessarily based on the inherent sensitivity characteristics of the digital object.

PIDs in a Sensitive Data Context

For 'open' data, the repository focus is often on providing access through a direct download to a researcher's desktop. The access to and use of some digital objects is restricted because they are deemed sensitive in some way, or exhibit some level of perceived risk e.g. commercial confidentiality. For repositories that provide infrastructure and services for sensitive digital objects their role is extended, beyond granting initial access, to mediating re-use.

The nature of the sensitivity will influence how the objects should be handled and what metadata is required. Sensitivity may be externally defined e.g. "These 11 herbs and spices are commercially sensitive" or "all minutes from these meetings will remain confidential for 50 years". Sensitivity may also be governed by inherent properties of digital objects e.g. environmental: "the exact geographic location of this rare species must not be made public".

The most common form of sensitivity handled by social science repositories is personal data about living human subjects. These digital objects either directly identify humans, or could be used to do so in conjunction with other information. The primary risk mitigation activity in these environments is to prevent re-identification of those subjects. Perspectives vary, and it is not always possible to distinctly separate data and metadata. Descriptions of variables and frequency statistics may be treated as metadata, but can themselves be disclosive and require associated sensitivity information. These inherent properties of the digital objects may be amenable to empirical assessment of disclosure risks but this is a non-trivial exercise and can be exponentially more difficult as the number of variables increases

Once some or all of the data, metadata and documentation in a digital object is classified with some level of sensitivity, there is a need to manage access and define permitted use.

In defining the semantics for persistent identifiers for digital objects, we need to consider the relevant component parts of a PID-driven object model.

- PID Identifier String
- PID Resolution Method/PID Manager Resolution Target (see Appendix)
- PID metadata
 - Kernel metadata - critical metadata that should always accompany a PID
 - Other PID metadata - that the PID Service Provider supports
- Intermediate metadata (including landing page/catalogue record content when PID doesn't route directly to a digital object)

- Target digital object
 - Data
 - Has parts
 - Metadata
 - Has parts
 - Documentation
 - Has parts

If some or all parts of the target digital objects' data, metadata and documentation are deemed sensitive then their access and use will be controlled. Parts may be assigned their own PIDs and have their own metadata; these may require their own independent sensitivity assessments and status information.

'Intermediate' metadata on a catalogue or landing page will often be a subset of the metadata the repository holds within and about the digital object. Unless the information is a 'tombstone'¹, then this will usually include a method for gaining access to the digital object. This information may or may not be machine-readable or machine actionable.

In addition to assigning a unique identifier string and providing a resolution method (so that a PID Manager can provide the target digital object location), PID Service providers may support a range of metadata elements. This metadata can vary across providers.

'Kernel' metadata is a notional set of metadata elements that would ideally be common across all persistently identified digital objects² and available across all endpoints. In addition to the typical ID string and location, these may include version metadata, related object metadata, integrity metadata, object type information and 'policies'. Examples of policies provided by the RDA paper include 'object license', "This should be of type PID or URL, pointing to a stable identifier for the object's license".

For sensitive digital objects some metadata may be sensitive (see above) but to support PID resolution to targets (object, or intermediate metadata) and routes from intermediate metadata to digital objects, *some* metadata *must* be open.

Gaps in PID Semantics for Sensitive Data

Which gaps in current PID semantics need to be filled to maximise their functionality, including machine-actionability, for sensitive digital objects? Which contextual assumptions can we make about sensitive PID use to inform our perspective and define fit for purpose transparent metadata to support sensitive data access, protection and use? In cases where a human or machine cannot directly access and interrogate a digital object due to its sensitivity, how do we maximise what they *can* do with the accessible metadata? Can

¹ Retained record of a digital object that has been deleted, or removed from the system

² Weigel, T., Plale, B., Parsons, M., Zhou, G., Luo, Y., Schwardmann, U., Quick, R., Hellström, M., & Kurakawa, K. (2019). RDA Recommendation on PID Kernel Information (Version 2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.15497/rda00031>

we standardise and align the process from sensitive data classifications, to machine actionable rights and access management?

Some ‘object licence’ information in kernel metadata may route to a machine-readable licence e.g. creative commons. For fully open data, a simple link to the digital object may be provided that can be identified and negotiated by humans or machines (“download here”). However, for sensitive digital objects licences may be more complex, with a range of permissions, prohibitions and obligations. While the sensitive data licence itself will usually outline usage rights for the digital object, it does not typically define access routes and barriers. Digital object managers may be familiar with their local set of ‘access conditions’, but less familiar with the granular sensitivity of objects and parts of objects they care for.

Licences, and more broadly ‘rights management information’, should, in part, be a function of the sensitivity status of the digital object, that deterministically informs access management and reuse criteria. The provision of a kernel metadata link to ‘something about rights’ is too generalised to be consistently machine actionable, as it is not informative about the sensitivity of the target or barriers/steps to access.

At present, it is not common for rights information to be presented in a machine actionable form, such as Open Digital Rights Language (ODRL)³. Nevertheless, even if this were the case, extensions would be required to support sensitivity classifications, and their impact on sensitive data handling workflows. The 5 Safes Framework⁴ for sensitive data implies the need for a range of extension metadata and entities (with associated PIDs) to support workflows:

Safe Data: The identified digital object.

Safe Projects: the intended use is acceptable and approved. Often precluding direct machine access and requiring humans in the loop.

Safe People: identified people (cf: ORCID) with appropriate knowledge (training and qualifications) and permissions (authentication and authorisation)

Safe Settings: access and use may be restricted to specific environments such as secure remote access SecureLab, safe room or Trusted Research Environment (TRE).

Safe Outputs: subsets of, and links between data undertaken as part of research must be approved as non-disclosive before they are ‘output’ from safe settings.

Safe outputs may receive their own PID to enable data citation. Some publications will be based on conclusions from research results that cannot be made public due to their sensitivity classification. This latter case raises the need to assign PIDs to new digital objects that are the ‘products’ of data subsetting or linkage, which cannot be made public,

³ <https://www.w3.org/TR/odrl-model/>

⁴ <https://ukdataservice.ac.uk/help/secure-lab/what-is-the-five-safes-framework/>

but must be citable. This has related implications for the long-term retention and active preservation of these digital objects.

Taken together we have sensitivity assessments of digital objects that imply a requirement for infrastructure (e.g. secure research environments) and services (e.g. project evaluation, user training) and inform rights statements, which guide permitted and protected routes to access.

The journey of digital object discovery, for humans and machines will often begin with a search of aggregated metadata such as that harvested from PID providers. While standards do exist for assigning sensitivity classification information to digital objects (e.g. Data Privacy Vocabulary- DPV⁵) it is far more common for repositories and other data providers to use a wide range of proprietary 'sensitivity levels' or to imply sensitivity by applying 'access levels' such as 'Restricted' or 'Controlled'. Global alignment on a common metadata set for describing digital object sensitivity seems unlikely in the medium term.

However, at the aggregated metadata search level a user may find it valuable to narrow a search to digital objects with the kind of human-level data that meets their research needs. Conversely, a user may wish to restrict a search only to digital objects that are entirely *open and without restrictions on access*⁶, either to humans or machines. These scenarios imply a benefit to providing items of metadata beyond a simple 'link to rights':

1. Digital Object is/is not sensitive
2. Digital Object is/is not immediately available for access by
 - a. Human
 - b. Machine

Providing this binary metadata at the kernel level would enrich support for resource discovery. Both could and should be linked to further information that elaborates on the schemas and scales used to define sensitivity, and the routes and methods provided for access.

If there are barriers to sharing sensitivity level information at the object level, some related metadata at the repository level may have value, particularly for researchers looking to deposit their metadata. A researcher seeking to deposit data could search for a repository that specifically states that it supports sensitive data, or implies it by providing secure research infrastructure. A researcher seeking to maximise the use of their fully open data may wish to select a repository that supports bulk machine harvesting of the digital objects themselves - with no intermediary logins or click through that only support human users.

Even with this sensitivity and human/machine access information available as metadata at the object and/or repository level, barriers to human and machine access to metadata and digital objects remain. At the initial PID metadata level there is no method to formally

⁵ <https://w3c.github.io/dpv/2.2/dpv/>

⁶ As noted above, this is not automatically guaranteed by the presence of a standard 'open licence'.

express what a PID finally resolves to or the intermediate links in that journey. Ideally the metadata payload would include information on the next machine-actionable step, how it should be negotiated, how many degrees of separation it is from the target object, and whether the ultimate resolution target is the digital object or a metadata description.

Gaps Résumé & Recommendations

Taken together we have sensitivity assessments of digital objects that imply a requirement for infrastructure (e.g. secure research environments) and services (e.g. project evaluation, user training) and inform rights statements, which guide permitted and protected routes to access.

There is a lack of a robust model and schema to support the interplay of sensitivity, rights and access. Such a schema would support metadata sharing for discovery, clear routing from PID to metadata/object, and clarity on barriers to access for humans and machines. Clear modelling would support standard methodologies for building ODRL rights statements with appropriate extensions to support information about sensitive data infrastructure, services and access routes.

In the absence of a single common approach to describing sensitivity, transparency of classifications should be supported and encouraged, that is to say, usage of a term such as 'open' should be supported by a clear definition of what such a term means in the local context of the individual repository. Sensitivity assessment outcomes should be supported by information - as quantitative as practicable - that clarifies whether they are based on inherent properties of the digital object, or external factors such as national legislation (e.g. GDPR), organisational policy, or data owner sensitivity to public opinion. Two objects with the same 'access level' that require permission, training and use within a secure research environment are not necessarily of equivalent sensitivity. It is important for repositories to understand whether one is the result of an overcautious depositor with a desire to minimise access to their data, while another contains individual level data points about identifiable humans.

As sensitive data objects are changed, split and merged, their sensitivity status will need to be re-assessed, with a consequent impact on rights statements, access criteria and their persistent identifier. Maintaining alignment between these changes alongside a history of object changes delivers clear provenance and engenders trust in the assertions of sensitivity status

In addition to generic links to licence information from the PID metadata kernel, there is potential value in exposing high-level statements about sensitivity status and/or access barriers to data.

PID metadata, including kernel metadata, is a key resource for aggregated discovery systems. Currently it is missing adequate information about the sensitivity of the target object or its parts.

Mapping out the machine actionable journey from PID to objects and their parts - c.f. 'transitive dereferencing' in the introduction - would streamline discovery, analytics, access and use for file based and linked open data collections of digital objects.

Together these steps would ensure that sensitive digital objects remain as open as possible while maintaining legal and ethically required barriers to access that ensure that they are as protected as necessary.

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